

MARVIC
MRV for carbon farming

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Analysis of Current MRV Systems

MARVIC

Deliverable 1.1

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Summary

The concept of quality criteria is a fundamental aspect addressed by crediting standards in carbon farming globally. However, significant variations exist in how these criteria are addressed and the accuracy of the methods employed. Consequently, this divergence results in carbon credits of varying performance within the Voluntary Carbon Market. This comparative analysis of quality criteria proposed in 11 existing MRV methodologies applied including private certification standards (Verra, Gold Standard, Plan Vivo, and MoorFutures), public standards (Label Bas-Carbone, UK Woodland Carbon Code and UK Peatland Code), and independent international bodies (GHG Protocol and the Integrity Council for Voluntary Carbon Market). We highlight the divergence between actual standards and propositions under the Carbon Removal Certification Framework, particularly in five quality criteria: additionality, permanence, leakage, baseline and double counting. By examining these variations, this review sheds light on the challenges and opportunities for enhancing the consistency and robustness of carbon offsetting practices in agricultural contexts. While for a deeper analysis, evaluation of the limitations in existing methodologies, forward-thinking solutions, recommended practices for forthcoming strategies, and expert analyses are included in MARVIC Deliverable 1.2 Draft Rules and Guiding Principles for the MRV Framework.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ABBREVIATIONS /ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
BAU	Business As Usual
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CDP	Carbon Disclosure Project
CF	Carbon Farming
CORSIA	Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation
CRCF	Carbon Removals Certification Framework
CRETA	Carbon Removal Expert Group Technical Assistance
DG Clima	Directorate-General for Climate Action
EC	European Commission
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GHG LS&R	Greenhouse Gases Land Sector & Removals
GS	Gold Standard
GSVER	Gold Standard Voluntary Emissions Reduction
ICROA	International Carbon Reduction and Offset Alliance
ICVCM	Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LBC	Label Bas-Carbone
LUST	Land Use X Soil Type
NDC	Nationally Determined Contributions
SBTi	Science Based Target Initiative

SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
VCM	Voluntary Carbon Market
VCU	Verified Carbon Units

1. Introduction

In pursuit of the ambitious goal to become the world's first climate-neutral continent by 2050, the European Union has established the Green Deal as a cornerstone. This comprehensive strategy spans across all sectors of the economy, including industry, energy, transportation, and construction. The agricultural sector has a central role to play in the strategy towards neutrality: It is one of the only sectors capable of both reducing its emissions and removing CO₂ from the atmosphere, to store it in soils; thus regenerating soils biodiversity and exosystemic functions such as water resources management. In order to engage agriculture, and more broadly the land sector, in such a dynamic, the European Commission, with the Farm to Fork Strategy, introduced the concept of carbon farming and set to the land sector the ambitious objective to store to store 310 MT eq. from 2026 to 2030.

Removing CO₂ from the atmosphere to store it in soils is possible through carbon farming transition, but it involves costly, and sometimes risky, changes in farm management practices. Europe's political ambition is to use the voluntary carbon market to help finance, and sustain, this transition: by certifying carbon removals as carbon certificates sold on this market.

This mechanism requires a dedicated certification framework, with scientifically robust methods for measuring carbon removals and rules, or quality criteria, to certify the integrity and quality of carbon certificates. This is the ambition of the CRCF (Carbon Removal Certification Framework). In order to build this framework, the European Commission has set up an expert group and funds projects to work on rules and methods tailored to Carbon Farming in Europe, such as the MARVIC project.

MARVIC project is an EU Soil Mission, Horizon Europe -funded initiative, comprising 16 European partners across 12 countries, collaborating to develop MRV methodologies that will be harmonized at the European level and adaptable to various “Land Use X Soil Type” (LUST) contexts. Its objective is to conceive and test a harmonized yet context-specific framework for Carbon Farming, in alignment with the ambitions outlined by the Commission in CRCF.

The rules and methods proposed by the MARVIC Project for European Carbon Farming will have to meet the dual objective of scientific robustness and compatibility with the realities of the agricultural world (technical, economic and administrative) to ease the implementation of the projects and more broadly the monitoring, reporting and verification of soil carbon removals.

In this first deliverable, we present the first comparative analysis work carried out on the "guiding principles" of existing certification frameworks for carbon farming, as well as international standards recommendations that have an international normative vocation. These elements are also known as quality criteria and cover 5 areas according to international standards: Baselines, additionality, permanence, double counting, and leakage. The CRCF broadens the scope of quality criteria to include the quantification (also covered by international standards but more generally as a separate field), in the CRCF quality criteria's are addressed under the umbrella of the QU. A.L.I.TY acronym, standing for QUantification, Additionnality, Long-term storage, and sustainabiLLTY. This report deals exclusively with "qualitative" quality criteria (i.e. not quantification, broadly addressed in MARVIC work packages 3 and 4).

This public deliverable is complemented by other deliverables, for the moment non-public, which discuss for each quality criteria the most suitable proposals for the European CRCF. These reports will soon be communicated in the following order: baselines, additionality, permanence, double-counting and leakages. In the continuation of MARVIC's work, the different options proposed for each of these quality criteria will be discussed, evaluated, and compared in real conditions, for the main types of European agricultures. The objective is to equip the decision-maker with carbon farming MRV tools that propose the appropriate trade-off between scientific robustness and adaptability to real farm conditions.

Defining the right trade-off between scientific robustness and adaptability to real farm conditions.

Quality criteria are essential to create market trust in the carbon credits (or certificates), to reassure against the risk of greenwashing, therefore, to give a monetary value to the carbon certificate. They therefore play a key role in the politic objective of using the voluntary carbon market to finance the transition.

For these reasons, quality criteria are the subject of much discussion, and certification frameworks are responding to recent scandals on carbon credits integrity precisely by strengthening their processes and methodologies on quality criteria. But this race for safety has its downside, it increases project costs and shrinks the share of carbon money dedicated to directly finance the transition; also it creates farmers' rejection of ever more stringent and time-costly procedures.

The problem stems from the fact that voluntary carbon finance was created on the energy sector, and quality criteria are adapted to the energy sector realities. They are much more complicated to adapt to the economic and administrative realities of the agricultural sector, and to the biogeological specificities of biogenically stored carbon.

The challenge is therefore to design quality criteria that meet the realities of the agricultural sector (so that projects are acceptable to farmers) while meeting the robustness and integrity requirements of voluntary carbon finance.

EU CRCF can make a difference and create the 1st carbon farming framework suited to agriculture.

The analysis of existing methods shows a high variability, depending on the certification frameworks, for the quality criteria; Proposals mainly converge, but there is not yet a stable proposal that has gained consensus at the international level.

The CRCF's analysis shows that its proposals on quality criteria are generally convergent with the recommendations of international standards and with the main orientations taken by existing certification frameworks. They now need to be specified as to their application at the farm level and for the different types of agricultures. This is the objective of the MARVIC project Work Package 1, that will be based on this 1st literature review.

2. Review of existing methodologies

2.1. Inventory of current methodologies

Table 1 provides an overview of the selected MRV methodologies for this review. These methodologies, specifically focusing on SOC (Soil Organic Carbon) measurement, are prominent in the Carbon Farming (CF) sector due to their wide recognition and efficacy. The Woodland Carbon Code, Verra, Gold Standard, and Plan Vivo are listed in the ICROA (International Carbon Reduction and Offset Alliance) registry, which aims to promote best practices in carbon offsetting by encouraging transparency, integrity, and efficiency in emissions reduction and offset projects (ICROA, 2024). At the time of our research, Plan Vivo's SHAMBA methodology was still available, which was later integrated into the official PM001 methodology as a tool.

The Label Bas Carbone (LBC), on the other hand, is a French national certification framework, developed by the French government. The UK Woodland code is also a public standard backed by the Welsh government.

Furthermore, the MoorFutures and UK Peatland Code methodologies, specialized in certifying carbon credits for peatlands were selected. This diversity of methodologies ensures a comprehensive and rigorous approach to evaluating and certifying CF projects.

Table 1 List of selected methodologies.

Standard	Methodology	Date
Verra	VM0042 - V2.0	30/05/2023
	VM0036 – V1.0	17/07/2017
Gold Standard	SOC framework V1.0	01/2020
Plan Vivo	SHAMBA V2.0	03/11/2015
	PM001 V0.1	01/05/2022
Label Bas Carbon	<i>Grandes cultures - Arable crops</i> V1.1	23/07/2021
	<i>CarbonAgri – Livestock</i>	09/09/2019
	<i>Plantation de vergers – Orchards</i>	23/10/2020
UK Woodland Carbon Code	V2.2	20/04/2022
UK Peatland code	V2.0	03/2023
MoorFutures	Methodologie für MoorFutures-Projekte	02/2017

Our analysis of quality criteria in the carbon market extended beyond crediting standards to compass a holistic understanding of qualitative considerations:

- The GHG Protocol emerged as a reference, renowned for its role in facilitating greenhouse gas (GHG) accounting and reporting for companies, organisations, countries and cities. Notably, it has recently expanded its sectoral approaches to include a methodology tailored for the land sector, presently in a draft form. Its significance serves as a foundational reference for GHG accounting and is used by standards like ISO 14064, the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP), and the Science-Based Targets initiative (SBTi).
- The CORSIA (Compensation for Reduction of CO₂ Emissions in Air Transport) program is a carbon offset program designed to mitigate international aviation emissions. Through this programme, airlines are allowed to purchase carbon credits or offsets equivalent to their emitted CO₂ to compensate for their environmental impact, marking a pioneering market-based measure to offset carbon emissions.

- The Integrity Council for Voluntary Carbon Market (ICVCM) and its Core Carbon Principles furnish a framework aimed at safeguarding the quality and integrity of carbon credits, thereby enhancing the credibility of our analysis.

The choice of methodologies provides an overview, considering private certification standards (Verra, Gold Standard, Plan Vivo, MoorFutures), public standards (LBC, UK Woodland Carbon Code and UK Peatland Code) and independent international bodies (GHG Protocol, CORSIA and ICVCM).

2.2. Comparative analysis of qualitative criteria

2.2.1. Additionality

Additionality is defined as a demonstration that carbon removals and/or reduction in GHG emissions are associated with the adoption of new land management practices, greater than the business as usual scenario and would not happen without incentives from the carbon market (Batjes et al., 2023).

The need to demonstrate that the project became feasible due to the remuneration obtained from carbon credits is considered as key element to attest the additionality of a project. Thus, ICVCM defines in its Core Carbon Principles that the GHG emission reductions or removals from the mitigation activity shall be additional, meaning they would not have occurred in the absence of the incentive created by carbon credit revenues (ICVCM, 2022). Verifying the additionality of the project ensures that it has a positive impact on climate that would not have been possible without the carbon finance. Indeed, in a finance model, credits support the implementation of additional practices that yield positive impacts. Climate benefits alone cannot certify the additionality of the project. While planting hedges does sequester carbon, if the planting is subsidized under a third-party project or through programs like the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), it would not be eligible for carbon credit payments. The latest available definition of additionality in the elaboration of the Carbon Removals Certification Framework (CRCF) state that any activity shall be additional. The EU has proposed a method for certifying additionality when the standardised baseline is used. This reduces the administrative burden. However, if the specific baseline is chosen, then financial and regulatory additionality will have to be demonstrated (Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products, 2024). In the

CORSIA program, additionality is the first eligibility criterion and is defined by regulatory and climatic surplus. For the GHG protocol Land Sector and Removals (GHG LS&R) additionality is defined by financial means. The intervention (e.g., project or activity) reduces emissions or increases removals relative to the amount of emissions or removals that would have occurred without the incentives provided by the credit (World resources institute & WBCSD, 2022).

Additionality is assessed primarily through regulatory and financial conditions (in 72% of the analysed methodologies). The project activities must not be required by enforced regulations, requiring managers to implement more advanced and effective climate mitigation practices often resulting in more stringent measures. Financial additionality is proven by identifying possible fundings for project activities and proving it's not sufficient to support the change of practices. It can also be proven by demonstrating that the project is not the most economically attractive option or is not viable without the financing from the carbon credits.

Three alternative ways to prove additionality are also possible within certain methodologies:

- The identification of barriers that prevent the implementation of project activities is frequently used. This process involves identifying factors that impede the successful implementation of project activities. These barriers encompass various domains such as investment, technology, and institutional frameworks, as exemplified in methodologies like Verra VM0036. Moreover, some methodologies, such as the LBC, inherently incorporate barrier analysis into their framework, alleviating the initial burden on project developers. The methodology itself demonstrates the general barriers to the implementation of CF practices. Institutional barriers are also often regarded in barrier analysis approaches. These barriers can vary significantly depending on the local context, influenced by factors such as land ownership structures, social norms, and cultural practices. Barriers associated with accessing investments or technology are generally easier to pinpoint when compared to institutional barriers. This is due to their tangible nature, making them readily quantifiable or directly observable.
- The analysis of common practices within the local context serves as another method to attest the additionality of CF projects. This involves demonstrating that the practices to be implemented through the CF project are not commonly adopted in the area. Five methodologies incorporate this approach as a mean of verifying additionality. For instance,

Verra VM0042 establishes a threshold of 20% adoption to determine whether a practice is widespread in the region. Practices falling below this threshold are deemed uncommon, thereby indicating that the project introduces practices additional to those currently in use. Additionality in this context encompasses not only the introduction of new practices but also the discontinuation of mainstream practices or the adjustment of existing ones. While the preferred scale for analysis is typically local, the scope of analysis may vary. In methodologies such as the LBC - Orchard, the assessment of common practices involves examining trends in orchard surfaces at national level. A decreasing trend in orchard establishment suggests that starting a project would counter this, thereby making it additional. This approach underscores the importance of contextual analysis in determining the impacts of proposed CF practices.

- Finally, the evaluation of climatic benefits in comparison to Business-As-Usual (BAU) systems serves as a mean to attest additionality for Gold Standard and the LBC. This assessment is fundamental in establishing the viability and efficacy of a carbon farming project. It essentially determines whether the project contributes positively to mitigating climate change. If there are no carbon sequestration, there are no credits issued and the project is therefore worthless. It's noteworthy, however, that while these methodologies rigorously evaluate the climatic benefits in terms of carbon sequestration, they do not explicitly address other potential environmental or ecological co-benefits. For instance, the positive impact on biodiversity or the enhancement of water resources are not accounted for in the evaluation process of additionality. However, Gold Standard developed a Safeguarding principles & requirements that must be respected by project developer. This procedure aims to address the multi-dimensional impacts of GS projects. It considers social, economic, environmental, and ecological requirements. Concerning environment, ecology and land use GS projects must promotes sustainable management, protection, conservation, maintenance and rehabilitation of natural habitats and their associated biodiversity and ecosystem functions (Gold Standard, 2023). This is not used to assess climatic additionality but is still mandatory to develop a project.

Gold Standard also developed a positive list to assess additionality. GS proposes 3 ways of demonstrating additionality. Either by using the CDM AM tool 02 v2.2, or by demonstrating an activity penetration of less than 5%, or by using the positive list as shown below.

This mechanism works as a list of criteria that projects must meet to ensure additionality:

- The project area is located in a country or in a region with the latest UNDP Human Development Indicator below or equal to 0.7 AND
- The project activities shall not be mandatory by any law or regulation, OR if they are mandatory, the Project Developer shall demonstrate that these laws or regulations are systematically not enforced. AND one of the followings:
 - The mean annual precipitation in the project area is less than 600 mm. OR
 - In the project area a minimum of 5 native crop species are being cultivated in a locally adapted agroforestry system. OR
 - The project is a smallholder project and results in Gold Standard VERs of less than 60,000 t CO₂ eq per annum. OR
- The project area is located in a country or region with a recent UNDP Human Development Indicator below 0.5, OR In a Small Island Developing State (SIDS).

It is important to note that additionality is never proven solely through a single parameter. All methodologies consider at least a combination of two parameters. The most common combination is regulatory and financial additionality. This combination is widely utilized, and the adoption of two distinct criteria is also prevalent. As mentioned earlier some methodologies like GS (V02.2) and Plan Vivo (V01) suggest using a CDP tool to assess additionality. It follows a decision tree, as pictured in Figure 1, to help project owner to demonstrate additionality and considers the identification of alternative scenario, barrier, (optional) investment and common practices analysis (UNFCCC & CDM, 2008).

Figure 1 Decision tree from the CDM tool to demonstrate additionality (UNFCCC and CDM, 2008)

Regulatory additionality is consistently factored into the analysis, except for Gold Standard, while financial additionality is explicitly employed by eight methodologies. However, when financial additionality is not explicitly considered, it is inherently addressed within the barrier analysis.

The consideration of other criteria is less mainstream. It is noteworthy that for some methods, it is the responsibility of the project developer to demonstrate additionality, whereas for the LBC, most criteria are already incorporated into the methodology. The project developer only needs to prove the financial additionality of the project.

Our findings align with those of the review conducted by the Expert Group working on the methodologies for the CRCF (CRETA). Their analysis of 26 methodologies for the agricultural sector/mineral soils demonstrates consistency with our results, highlighting the prevalence of similar dominant criteria and combinations. As depicted in Figure 1 below, the synthesis illustrates the frequency of each criterion. Notably, regulatory criteria were identified 20 times and financial criteria 16 times, emerging as the most utilized. Furthermore, these criteria are frequently combined, with the regulatory + financial requirements combination being the most used one, present in 14 methodologies. The expert group also noted that barrier analysis, common practices, and climatic performances were among the less developed criteria (about 6 or 7 times each). However, it is noteworthy that three methodologies utilize only climatic performance as a means to demonstrate the additionality of the project (Lesschen & Karsch, 2023).

Figure 2 Frequency of appearance of additionality criteria in the methodologies studied by CRETA (Lesschen & Karsch, 2023)

Therefore, this review has brought attention to the considerable variability in the assessment of additionality across different standards. While there appears to be a consensus regarding regulatory and financial criteria, the methodologies employed to demonstrate additionality exhibit variation. Furthermore, barriers and common practices analysis do not consistently consider the same criteria across standards, resulting in differing levels of precision and threshold. This underscores that although additionality is consistently demonstrated by standards, projects may not be comparable within the VCM.

Table 2 Assessment of additionality criteria in 11 MRV methodologies.

Methodology	Regulatory	Financial	Barrier analysis	Common practices	Climatic
Plan vivo - SHAMBA	Activities must not be required by enforced legislation or conducted to fulfil the official policies, regulations, or industry standards or any organisation or institution.	-	Identify barriers that would prevent the implementation of project activities (financial, technical, institutional, political, ecological, social, cultural).	-	-
Plan Vivo - PM001	-	Simple cost analysis.	Identify barriers that would prevent the implementation of at least one alternative land use scenario (Investment, institutional, technological, local tradition, prevailing practice and ecological conditions, social conditions, land tenure/ ownership/ inheritance/ property rights).	Identify similar activities and assess the essential distinctions between projects. If there is no differences the project is not considered additional.	-
LBC – Arable	The baseline must comply with the obligations arising from legislative and regulatory texts. Project owners must define and justify the chosen baseline.	Assess the level of public and private funding received for implementing or maintaining practices and demonstrate they are insufficient to implement the project.	Demonstration of general barriers to the implementation of low-carbon practices in the methodology.	-	Only emission reductions that go beyond this reference scenario are recognized within the framework of the label.

		Otherwise, buffer = 20%.			
LBC - Cattle	The baseline must comply with the obligations arising from legislative and regulatory texts. Project owners must define and justify the chosen baseline.	If CEEs* are issued after the project has been implemented: 20% buffer on emission reductions relating to energy consumption covered. If a methanization unit is installed during the project: demonstrate the absence of windfall effects by analyzing the financing plan for the methanization unit	Demonstration of general barriers to the implementation of low-carbon practices in the methodology (skills, investments, risk aversion).	Analysis of carbon intensity trends for meat and dairy product in the methodology.	-
LBC – Orchard	The baseline must comply with the obligations arising from legislative and regulatory texts. Project owners must define and justify the chosen baseline.	Inventory of public subsidies potentially eligible and demonstrate they are insufficient (represent less than 50% of the investment cost).	Demonstration of general barriers to the implementation of low-carbon practices in the methodology (financial recovery and risk aversion).	Analysis of the decreasing orchard surface area in the methodology. Planting orchards is no longer a common practice.	-
Verra – VM0042	The project proponent must demonstrate regulatory surplus.	-	Identify institutional barriers that would prevent implementation of a change in pre-existing practices.	Demonstrate that adoption of project activities is not common practice in the region (20% adoption rate).	-
Gold Standard	Not mandatory.	Demonstrate Financial Additionality and	-	Activity penetration <5% of farmers in the reference area.	Demonstrate impacts are additional

		Ongoing Financial Need.			compared to the baseline scenario (benefits goes beyond BAU).
UK Woodland Carbon code	Activities must not be required by enforced legislation. Compensatory plantation or reforestation are not eligible.	Demonstrate that project activities are not economically attractive or viable.	-	-	-
UK Peatland Code	Peatlands should not be subject to regulatory restoration requirements.	At least 15% of project activities must be financed by carbon credits.	-	-	-
Moor Futures	Development under support program possible but constrained by limited resources or logistical challenges.	Demonstrate that project activities are not economically viable.	-	-	-
Verra – VM0036	Activities must not be required by enforced legislation.	-	Identify investment, technological and institutional barriers.	Demonstrate that adoption of project activities is not common practice in the region.	-

- No information was provided in the methodology

2.2.2. Permanence

According to the IPCC, permanence is the longevity of a carbon pool and the stability of its stocks, given the management and disturbance environment in which it occurs (IPCC, 2000). Ensuring the permanence of carbon storage in carbon farming projects is crucial for effective participation in financial mechanisms like the VCM. Permanence guarantees that carbon emission reductions are long-lasting and genuinely contribute to mitigating climate change over the long term. Without this assurance, investors and carbon credit buyers could face a high risk of emissions reduction goals not being met. Confidence in permanence is therefore paramount to instil trust in the credibility and reliability of carbon farming projects within the VCM framework. It provides assurance that investments made towards carbon sequestration efforts yield lasting environmental benefits, aligning with the overarching objectives of climate change mitigation. Yet, guaranteeing permanence in natural systems poses challenges. The storage of carbon in soil is reversible, emphasizing the need for continuous soil carbon management practices. Changes in soil carbon content are non-linear, with the most significant changes occurring initially and reaching a new equilibrium over several decades. After changes in land use, carbon gain lags behind carbon loss, leading to a 'slow in - fast out' pattern (Chotte & Weill, 2021). Various risks threaten the permanence of carbon storage, from natural events like droughts and wildfires to management practices such as discontinuing beneficial practices or reintroducing tillage (McDonald et al., 2021). Moreover, the full effects of climate change are not yet entirely understood, so feedback loops are likely to have a significant impact on permanence, as extreme events could be amplified. For some NGOs and industrialists, since the removals linked are to living organisms it cannot, intrinsically, be permanent, and they should be excluded from the certification framework. Consequently, only technological absorptions should be considered (Grimault, 2023). Permanence is thus pivotal in ensuring that carbon credits sold represent long-term storage contributing effectively to climate change mitigation, itself a long-term process. In its latest version, the CRCF acknowledges that soils emissions reductions and removal linked to carbon farming are temporary. They are considered to be released once the monitoring period is over, and only renewed monitoring can ensure long-term storage. The commission has therefore chosen to differentiate long-term storage from the temporary storage offered by carbon farming.

Accordingly, permanence is systematically considered into carbon certification methodologies, as summarized in the Table 3 below. The risk of non-permanence is generally measured using a matrix of risk factors. The strategies developed to address potential carbon releases are mainly based on a buffer approach. Under this approach, offset credits from individual projects are set

aside into a common buffer reserve (or “pool”), which functions as an insurance mechanism. Reserved credits can be drawn upon to compensate for reversals from any project. If a reversal occurs, credits are retired or cancelled from the buffer reserve on behalf of the project’s buyers. Two approaches are used under the standards analysed either the definition of a buffer specific to the risks associated with the project, or a standard mandatory buffer set at the start of the project.

Mandatory appointed buffers are used in both the LBC and MOORfuture methodologies. The LBC applies a 20% buffer on carbon removal for its arable crops and cattle methodologies. If the project is renewed, then the buffer amount drops to 10% for the reconducted period. For orchard planting, a consistent 10% buffer is applied due to perceived lower anthropogenic, climatic, and biotic risks. This decision is influenced by factors such as the substantial investment required for orchard establishment, which decreases the likelihood of farmers discontinuing their activities. Orchards also exhibit reduced susceptibility to fire and storm damage owing to their low planting density and specific design. Additionally, rigorous technical monitoring of pests and diseases helps mitigate risks of outbreaks. MOORfuture assesses the risk of peat extension, invalidating the project if such risk is projected within the next 100 years. In the absence of peat exhaustion, a mandatory buffer of 30 % is applied.

In the majority of methodologies, **risk assessment tools** are used to evaluate the potential of non-permanence risks associated with carbon sequestration projects. These tools are used to determine the appropriate allocation of buffers based on the probability of occurrence of predefined risks. They analyse various factors such as natural events, management practices, and ecosystem dynamics to assess the likelihood of carbon storage reversibility over time. Thus, it ensures that carbon credits represent carbon that will be securely sequestered over the course of the project. These tools are often presented in the form of a matrix that takes into account the type of risk in relation to the probability of it occurring in the context of the project. Risks can be classified into different categories depending on the methods used. They can be categorized into three divisions:

1. As social, economic, environmental, technical, administrative risks, or
2. Natural Disturbance, political, project management, financial, market risks, or
3. Internal (project management, longevity, financial viability, opportunity cost), external (land and resources tenure, community engagement, political risk), and natural risks.

Hazard Categories	Identified Hazards and Impact on Permanence of Improved Condition (Add rows as necessary)	Risk Rating Without Controls			Mitigation Strategy	Risk Rating With Controls		
		L	C	R		L	C	R
Restoration Activities	Dams not creating a hydrological seal with the base of the drain and water finding a new path through underneath the dam	3	4	12	Experienced Project Staff and contractors	2	4	8
	Presence of peat pipes and sub-surface drainage	2	3	6	Where location known measures attempt made to disrupt/block	1	3	3
	Incorrect seed material applied e.g. reprofiled hagg slope seeded with Sphagnum which may establish successfully on the lower portions of the slope where it is wetter but may fail on the upper portions of the slope due to drier conditions)	3	4	12	Revegetate with donor turves where available or introduce a mix of plants during revegetation (wet and dry species)	2	4	8
	Reprofiled hagg too steep - soil and water movement preventing colonisation of introduced plants	3	4	12	Experienced Project Staff and contractors	2	4	8
Management Activities	Scrub establishment leading to drying of peat	2	2	4	Removal of tree seedlings over 1m in height	1	2	2
Extreme Weather	Hard frosts, storms, intense rainfall events could reverse attempts to re-vegetate e.g. wash brush and seeds off the soil surface.	4	4	16	Choose suitable vegetation mixture and revegetation method for climate	2	4	8
Geological Events	Landslips/peat slides within restoration area exposing areas of bare peat	2	4	8	Ensure restoration activities and methods minimise areas of unstable peat	2	4	8
Fire	Uncontrolled muirburn or wildfire removing vegetation	2	4	8	Cessation of muirburn on adjacent land	1	4	4
Other	n/a			0				0

13-25 = Unacceptable
9-12 = Tolerable
4-8 = Adequate
1-3 = Acceptable

Figure 3 UK Woodland Carbon code risk matrix (Woodland Carbon Code, 2022)

The project owner may use any type of credible information to support his statements, including but not limited to scientific report, studies, historic data, pictures, maps, credible websites, aerial imagery, CVs, legal documents, etc. The project developers therefore ensure that the carbon will be permanently stored over the certification period of the project, which is generally at least 5 years. Another approach developed only by the UK Woodland Carbon Code is to use an **assessment tool and establish a contract** with the carbon farmer to ensure that he will maintain good practices and therefore that the permanence of carbon storage will be preserved for as long as the contract is in force. It is also the only methodology to consider risk mitigation strategy and to review the risk level after the implementation of these practices.

Thus, this review of different standards demonstrates that although CF is a reversible phenomenon, it appears that standards strive to prove the permanence of carbon storage in their projects. The use of buffers illustrates that it is easier to implement mechanisms to account for reversibility rather than to mitigate the risk itself. It is noteworthy to mention that this mechanism is still quite subjective as the project developer rates the risks either by affecting a corresponding “high”, “medium”, “low” or a number on a scale, risk of occurrence to it. The matrix mechanisms help to list potential risks and reflect on their probability to happen in the project. However, it depends on the perception of the project owner. Furthermore, in the methods analysed, long-term storage is not really guaranteed because it only considers the duration of crediting and there is no post-project monitoring.

Table 3 Assessment of permanence criteria in 11 MRV methodologies.

Methodology	Permanence assessment	Risk buffer	Risk factors considered
Plan vivo - SHAMBA	Risk assessment with a matrix (social, economic, environmental, technical, administrative).	Risk defined for ex-ante credits: low = 12/20%, medium = 20/40%, High 40/60% and for ex-post credits: low = 5/10%, medium = 10/20%, high = 20/40%.	Social, economic, environmental, technical, and administrative.
Plan Vivo -PM001	Not mentioned apply calculation of a 90% confidence interval for sampling and modelling.	-	Social, economic, environmental, technical, and administrative.
LBC – Arable	Mandatory appointed buffer.	20% on carbon removal and 10% if the project is renewed.	-
LBC - Cattle	Mandatory appointed buffer.	20% on carbon removal, 10% on carbon removal in hedges.	-
LBC – Orchard	Mandatory appointed buffer.	10% on carbon removal.	-
Verra – VM0042	Risk assessment ratings on a 100y period.	Multiplication of the non-permanence risk by the net change in carbon stocks.	Internal, external and natural.
Gold Standard	Risk assessment with a transparent quantitative scoring approach.	20% for projects applying LUF requirements.	Natural disturbance, political, project management, financial and market risks.
UK Woodland Carbon code	Risk assessment tool + evidence of contracts with or a signed commitment statement from the landowner.	20% of net carbon sequestration.	Restoration activity, management, extreme weather, geological event, fire, other.
UK Peatland Code	Risk assessment on restoration + mitigation strategy for identified risk and resulting level of risk after controls.	15% to the Peatland code buffer.	Restoration activity, management, extreme weather, geological event, fire, other.
Moor Futures	Assessment of possible peat exhaustion in the project area over the next 100 years and exclusion from emission calculation + mandatory appointed buffer.	30% buffer zone.	Peat exhaustion in the next 100 years risk.
Verra – VM0036	Risk assessment ratings on a 100y period.	Multiplication of the non-permanence risk by the net change in carbon stocks.	Internal, external and natural.

-No information was provided in the methodology

2.2.3. Leakages

Leakages in carbon farming projects refer to consequences where actions taken to mitigate carbon emissions in one area unintentionally led to increased emissions or decreased carbon sequestration in another. These can occur due to various factors such as displacement of activities, changes in land use, or shifts in market dynamics. In order to define whether leakage is taking place, it is therefore necessary to define project boundaries. Methodologies used to assess the impact of carbon farming interventions define which sources of GHG and which carbon sinks are relevant to an activity and must be included in the project boundary to properly measure the impact of the intervention. Some methodologies may include leakage emissions directly in the calculation of (net) emission reductions, while others may account for leakage emissions separately. Leakage is context-specific; hence carbon farming projects might include different sources of leakage. Leakage from upstream/downstream emissions involves emissions that occur before or after a mitigation activity in the agricultural chain, influenced by the activity itself. For instance, methane emissions from natural gas production represent a upstream emission associated with fuel used in the project. Often, these emissions are considered directly in the quantification methods. Activity-shifting leakage occurs when the mitigation activity causes emissions to relocate, potentially to areas not targeted by the activity. An example is the displacement of agricultural activities from land that is afforested as part of the project. Market leakage arises when mitigation activities impact the supply or demand of emissions-intensive products or services, thus altering emissions elsewhere. For example, reduced wheat yields within a project area may drive increased harvesting in other regions to meet demand for wheat products. These economic leakages occur when market demand remains constant while local supply diminishes. Ecological leakage occurs when a mitigation activity indirectly affects emissions in hydrologically connected areas. For instance, lowering the water level in a wetland due to project implementation may lead to increased carbon dioxide emissions from soils. Understanding and addressing these various forms of leakage is crucial for the effective implementation of carbon farming initiatives.

To address them, methodologies employed in carbon farming projects try to incorporate monitoring and verification systems to ensure that the intended emission reductions or carbon sequestration are accurately accounted for. However, critics argue that the current approach to address leakage lacks the necessary rigor for long-term effectiveness, sparking controversy over the most suitable mitigation strategies. Discussions point out that nature-based offsets currently in use consistently underestimate the true extent of market leakage effects, raising concerns about

the accuracy of mitigation impact assessments. Failure to accurately assess and quantify leakage could result in the issuance of credits that significantly overstate actual emission reductions, potentially undermining climate policy objectives if widely utilized as offsets. Additionally, the context-specific nature of leakage emphasizes the importance of carefully designing interventions to minimize their adverse effects and ensure the integrity of emission reduction efforts (Filewod & McCarney, 2023).

To counter this, international guidelines recommend having a conservative approach. The GHG Protocol state that : GHG reductions or removals credits mitigate the risk of displacing impact elsewhere and account for any increase in GHG emissions or decrease in GHG removals outside of the project boundary that result from the intervention (World resources institute & WBCSD, 2022). The ICVCM defines that all material sources of leakage must be taken into account and minimized with deductions applied for residual leakage. Estimation of leakage have to be robust and conservative due to uncertainty. It should consider upstream/ downstream emissions, activity-shifting, market and ecological leakage (ICVCM, 2022). While under the CRCF proposal, leakage is only addressed in term of indirect land use change due to a decrease in food production. The only recommendation to date is that the benefits of a CF project should outweigh the carbon leakage (Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products, 2024).

However, it is essential to note that not all of these criteria are consistently addressed together in practice. Frequently, as shown in Table 4, only economic leakage factors are taken into account. Among the 11 methodologies reviewed, activity shifting is mentioned in six instances, while market leakage is referenced four times. Moreover, the consideration of both factors is prevalent, indicating that when multiple criteria are evaluated, they are typically examined together. Distinguishing between activity shifting and market leakage can be challenging as both entail the displacement of emissions. In this analysis, market leakage is considered when displacement arises from a reduction in production on the project lands. On the other hand, ecological leakage is only acknowledged twice, and only within peatland methodologies as other carbon farming methodologies, such as Gold or VERRA VM0042, restrain project eligibility to land that are not peatland and thus not hydrologically connected to other areas. It is noteworthy that none of the methodologies identified upstream/downstream emissions leakage, which are commonly integrated directly into emissions quantification methods. Remarkably, leakage considerations are

absent in LBC methodologies, indicating a lack of consideration for the potential trade-offs associated with the projects.

The approaches to assessing leakage across various methodologies exhibit significant diversity, reflecting the complex nature of leakage and the diverse contexts in which projects operate. In some cases, projects must demonstrate the absence of leakage under the applicability conditions of the methodology (Verra VM0036), while in others, quantification is required (Verra VM0042). The concept of ecological leakage, which relates to hydrogeological connectivity and its implications for emissions displacement, is predominantly addressed by methodologies focusing on peatlands, albeit not consistently as it's not included in the UK Peatland Code. Moreover, methodologies employ different strategies to address identified leakage. For instance, the Plan Vivo methodology incorporates a discount factor if activity shifting is identified, incentivizing robust mitigation efforts. Alternatively, for market leakage the methodology relies on the design of the project to prove it cannot happen in this specific context. For example, given that Plan Vivo projects are exclusively implemented in regions where participants are engaged in subsistence and small-scale production, market leakage risks are considered insignificant. Another option is to define a threshold under which leakage are considered negligible.

These divergent methods for addressing leakage across standards present a significant challenge to achieving effective climatic benefits. This lack of uniformity complicates the comparison and aggregation of emission reductions across projects and standards, hindering efforts to accurately measure and account for global emission reductions. Moreover, inconsistent leakage methodologies can undermine the integrity of carbon offset projects. If leakage is not adequately addressed or if methodologies differ in their leakage assessment criteria, there is a risk that emissions reductions achieved by one project may be offset by increased emissions elsewhere, resulting in no net reduction in greenhouse gas emissions at the global level. This diversity underscores the need for tailored approaches to leakage assessment that consider the unique characteristics of each project and LUST, while also ensuring robust mitigation of potential adverse impacts on climate and the environment.

Table 4 Assessment of leakage accounting in 11 MRV methodologies.

Methodology	Activity shifting	Market leakage	Ecological leakage
Plan Vivo -PM001	Describe all potential sources of leakage and any leakage mitigation measures. A leakage discount factor for emissions sources and carbon pool must be calculated.	Since projects can only take place in areas where the participants are involved in subsistence and small-scale production, market leakage from changes to the activities of project participants does not need to be included in the carbon accounting.	-
LBC – Arable, livestock, orchards	-	-	-
Verra – VM0042	Leakage assessed if GHG emissions > 5% of the project's climatic benefits.		-
	Leakage assessed if GHG emissions > 5% of the project's climatic benefits. Must consider new application of organic amendments from outside the project area, and livestock displacement.	Leakage considered if production decline more than 5% over a 10y period. Project developer must also consider leakage from diversion of biomass residues used for energy applications in the baseline scenario.	-
Gold Standard	-	Identify the potential carbon losses resulting from yield reduction and estimates the impact on the carbon stocks on the land to which the activity	Projects are not allowed on wetlands, where C runoff could be an issue. Leakage from C runoff is thus considered 0.

		would be the most likely to be shifted.	
UK Woodland Carbon code	If the project induces change of use or management of land within the same agricultural area, leakage must be accounted if GHG emissions >5% of the project climatic benefits.	-	-
UK Peatland Code	If the project induce change of use or management of land within the same agricultural area leakage must be accounted if GHG emissions >5% of the project climatic benefits.	-	-
Moor Futures	Demonstrate if the project induces land use change/ intensification outside the area and determine resulting GHG emissions, subtract it from the project climatic benefits.	-	If other ecosystem services are quantified, leakage should be determined according to the same rules.
Verra – VM0036	Demonstrate that peatland isn't exploited since at least 2 years prior the project (forestry, peat extraction, agriculture, food, fodder, fiber, fuel wood).	Demonstrate that peatland isn't exploited since at least 2 years prior the project (forestry, peat extraction, agriculture, food, fodder, fiber, fuel wood).	Demonstrate that there is no leakage by ensuring insignificant hydrological connectivity with adjacent area.

-No information was provided in the methodology

2.2.4. Baseline

A baseline in the context of carbon farming serves as a reference point against which the success of a carbon farming project is measured. Essentially, it represents the expected carbon stock change in the absence of any incentives for carbon removal enhancing practices. Establishing a robust baseline is crucial because it provides a benchmark to assess the actual carbon removals achieved through specific initiatives. This comparative analysis enables the quantification of additional carbon removals attributed to the implemented practices, forming the basis for assessing the project's environmental impact. The diversity in baseline methodologies arises from the varied agricultural and ecological landscapes. Different approaches, ranging from standardised models using agricultural reference data to site-specific assessments based on farmer activity and environmental parameters, cater to the complexity of ecosystems, soil types, and agricultural practices. Acknowledging this diversity is crucial for tailoring baseline methodologies to the specific characteristics of each agricultural setting, ensuring accurate and meaningful assessments of carbon sequestration initiatives.

Baselines can be broadly categorized into two types: **standardised baselines**, which represent average trends in carbon stocks derived from databases and comparable conditions, and **specific baselines**, which account for carbon stocks trends specific to a particular field or farm prior to the initiation of a CF project. Another distinction can be made regarding how to calculate the baseline. You can either **measure and remeasure SOC stocks** (with or without control plots) or **model SOC stocks changes**.

As the calculation methods to model baseline are multiparametric, it is not always easy to determine whether it is standardized or project specific. Indeed, certain parameters such as soil type may be specific to a farm, while activity data is extracted from regional databases. To understand this diversity of options, one must first comprehend the parameters included in modelling a baseline:

- The baseline determines the evolution of carbon stocks based on data related to soil, weather, management practices, and biomass production. It can be expressed as :
Evolution of SOC stocks (ton C/ha/year)
= $f(\text{soil, weather/climate, management practices, biomass})$
- Soil parameters impacting SOC are e.g., soil texture, mineralogy, initial SOC content.
- Weather/climate parameters are e.g., precipitation, air and soil temperature, evaporation.

- Management practices refer to all actions and decisions taken by a farmer (choice of crop types and varieties, fertilization, tillage, irrigation, crop residue management).
- Biomass production is influenced by soil quality, weather conditions, and farming practices. Crop growth is impacted by pedo-climatic conditions. Extreme weather events like droughts can significantly impact crop growth, especially in soils with poor texture or limited root space. Farmers employ various management practices to maximize crop growth within these conditions, though success may vary.

All these parameters can vary significantly from one farm to another, or even from one plot to another. The data used to define the baseline can thus be either very specific, very general, or a combination of both. However, the complexity in defining the baseline does not stop there. In addition to the specific/standardized distinction, temporal considerations must also be taken into account. In some cases, the baseline is defined as static, meaning it is calculated once at the beginning of the project and kept constant throughout the project's duration, or dynamic, which is recalculated.

The decisions regarding scale, calculation method, and timing have significant incidences on assessment criteria, including costs, cost distribution, data requirements, scalability, assurance of additionality, risks for farmers, and the types of farmers incentivized (early adopters, previously underperforming farmers, farmers with high carbon stocks).

According to the GHG Protocol any credited GHG reductions or removals must be calculated with a credible baseline. It is defined as a realistic, defensible, and conservative estimate of GHG reductions/ removals in the BAU scenario. For removals, a credible baseline may be zero if no removals are likely to occur in the absence of interventions (World resources institute & WBCSD, 2022). The ICVCM agrees on the need to have a conservative approach considering uncertainties (models, parameters, data sources, measurements). It specifies that the baseline must be updated or reviewed at a frequency that reflect changing circumstances (ICVCM, 2022). The CRCF opts for a standardized baseline by default with the possibility to use a specific approach in certain cases. The standardized baseline should reflect the performance of comparable activities in similar social, economic, environmental and technological circumstances and geographical locations (Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products, 2024).

In the examined methodologies, specific baselines are predominantly utilized (Table 5). However, in the context of the LBC, standardized baselines may be employed if farm specific data are not available, contrary to the approach advocated by the CRCF. To compensate for potential imprecision when using the standardized approach, the LBC applies a 10% buffer. This adjustment acknowledges that the more generalized the data are, the less precise the baseline reference becomes. Weather data often come from a local database from meteorological stations close by the project. It is not scalable to have stations directly in the fields. We observed a notable diversity in baseline precision among the standards analysed. Differences arise in various aspects, including the reference time period for baseline calculation (the year preceding the project for Shamba, 3 years for Verra, 5 years for Gold Standard), the scale of assessment (modelling unit for Gold Standard, farm level for LBC, project area > 5ha for UK Woodland Code), and the types of data utilized (satellite imagery for peatlands, SOC measurements for agricultural fields). Additionally, variations exist in the consideration of specific activity data depending on the methodology, with Verra assessing tillage practices, a factor not addressed by the LBC. Furthermore, the precision of the data utilized in calculations can range from tier 1 (emission factor applied to activity data) to tier 3 (direct measurement).

The measure and remeasure approach, although less developed, is presented as an option by Verra and Plan Vivo. However, the criteria for identifying matching control plots are stringent, encompassing factors such as similar topography, soil group and texture, SOC stocks, historical land cover and activity, climate zone, mean annual precipitation, and maximum distance between sites. This implies that identifying the appropriate control sites is difficult, but once they are established, it is possible to certify a larger number of projects/plots. This approach is still relatively new (May 2023 for Verra and November 2023 for Plan Vivo).

Thus, this review has brought to light the large complexity of baseline establishment. As essential as the baseline may be, there is no consensus across standards on how to calculate it. The accuracy of the baseline therefore varies greatly depending on the specificity of the input data to the models and the data considered. Once again, this variability between standards raises questions about the quality and comparability of the carbon credits available on the VCM. There is no consensus on the methodology to be used and the major reference standards such as the ICVCM do not provide precise information. The type of baseline needs to be adapted to the type of LUST, the quality of the data available, the economic impact and the ease of processing.

Table 5 Assessment of data requirements in 11 MRV methodologies.

Methodology	Modelling	Measure and remeasure
Verra – VM0036	Specific approach with a biophysical model Reference based over a 5-year period	Specific direct measurement of SOC changes on the project site possible if models are not available or parametrized for a region, crop or practice Reference based over a 3-year period Measurements of direct SOC changes between project and control sites. Reference based over a 5-year period
Plan vivo - SHAMBA	Specific approach (biomass burning, fertilization) with different level of accuracy in data inputs and standardised approach for yield Reference based over a 1-year period	NA
Plan Vivo -PM001	Based on expected changes within the project area (process-based models of changes in SOC) Emission factors applied to activity data	Measurements and modelling based on observations in matched control area
LBC – Arable	Specific approach preferred; standardised activity data possible if farm data unavailable and 10% buffer applied Reference based over a 3 year period	NA
LBC - Cattle	Specific approach preferred; standardised activity data possible if farm data unavailable and 10% buffer applied Reference based over a 1-year period	NA
LBC – Orchard	Specific approach Reference based over a 3-year period	NA
Gold Standard	Specific approach with models or default factors Reference based over a 5-year period	Specific measurement of SOC changes on the project site. Reference based over a 5-year period
UK Woodland Carbon code	Specific estimation of SOC stocks and inventory of existing trees, standardised data for other biomass types and SOC reference prior to planting Project smaller than 5ha are not subject to baseline assessment	NA
Verra – VM0042	'GEST' approach (Greenhouse gas Emission Site Type) uses ground vegetation composition and water table depth as proxies for peatland GHG emissions	NA
UK Peatland Code	Use of satellite imagery to define the initial state of the peatland, field measurement to confirm the imagery data, application of emission factors Reference based over the year 0 of the project	NA
Moor Futures	Use of satellite imagery, maps, pictures, publications and information from landowners and public authority to define the initial state of the peatland, application of emission factors Reference based over the year 0 of the project	NA

NA: not applicable

2.2.5. Double counting

Double counting is a central concern for CF projects. Indeed, poor traceability could result in the double counting of climate benefits from a same CF project. Moreover, there are various types of carbon credits on the VCM, causing confusion. Compensation credits, for instance, can be used by an external entity to claim reduction of its own emissions, as seen in the CORSIA mechanism for aviation. Conversely, contribution credits are not eligible for emission reduction accounting by the purchasing company. They are based on a voluntary principle where companies fund nature-based projects but cannot use emission reductions themselves. However, these reductions/sequestrations can still be accounted for by the states where the project takes place under the NDCs defined in the Paris Agreement. For a better understanding of mechanisms under the Article 6 of the Paris Agreement and their implications on carbon credits, please refer to (Lanckriet et al., 2024). In the context of the VCM, the most significant risks involve double use of a single credit, including multiple project developers certifying the same project (double issuance), multiple companies using credits from the same project (double use), or between the credit purchaser and a company whose lands are part of the CF project's Scope 3 emissions (double counting). Finally, double claiming arise from any situation in which the same GHG emission reduction or carbon removal is credited or claimed by more than one entity towards separate mitigation targets or emissions inventories (Verra Standard, 2023).

The risk of **double issuance** is effectively addressed by standards, all of which feature transparent registries of their carbon units. These registries typically include the quantity and type of certified emissions, project listings, and sometimes project developers' names, as seen in the LBC. The purpose of these registries is to provide publicly accessible and transparent data. Some standards also take precautions to avoid benefit overlaps between activities (GS, Verra, PV) and certification programs (Verra, GS). These overlap guarantees aim to prevent multiple emission reduction/sequestration activities or multiple standards in the same geographical area.

Regarding the **double use** of a carbon credit, this can occur through the use of the same credit by multiple parties. This issue is addressed by certain standards that define rules for the use of their credits (LBC, UK Woodland Carbon Code, GS, and Verra). These rules vary among standards. The LBC states that it is not possible to resell or transfer credits to a second buyer; only intermediary transactions are permitted. Gold Standard, UK Woodland and Peatland Code specify that sold credits must be clearly marked as withdrawn from the registry after purchase. The purchaser and beneficiary of the credits must also be clearly identified. Verra explicitly states that once the purchaser has withdrawn the credits, they cannot be used by other buyers, Verra,

or any other entity. Gold Standard is the only standard that defines penalties if these rules are not respected. These sanctions may include suspension of registry access or delisting.

Double counting between carbon credits and a company's Scope 3 emissions is considered in 2 methodologies. Verra opts for transparency by stating on companies' websites a comment explaining that the project activity has impacted the carbon footprint of a product. Gold Standard applies the recommendations of the GHG protocol by stating that it is the responsibility of companies to report accurately. Companies purchasing GSVERs should ensure that they do not report the GSVER towards a target or pledge if they are aware that another company is doing so.

Finally, **double claiming** of credit benefits by multiple entities is a subject that is addressed only minimally. Only Gold Standard and Verra have set up safeguards. This may be explained by the fact that some standards, such as the LBC, only issue contribution credits that will be used within the framework of NDCs and therefore cannot be claimed by companies, thus avoiding the risk of double counting. Gold Standard, on the other hand, applies the recommendations of the GHG protocol by stating that projects intending to avoid double claiming between the end-user of GSVERs and the NDC of the Host Country must receive an appropriate letter of authorization from the relevant Host Country and comply with Gold Standard's 'Requirements for Credits Authorized for Use Under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement'. Additionally, the Gold Standard Impact Registry functionality enables its carbon credits to be labelled as authorized and correspondingly adjusted under Article 6. Verra has also implemented an Article 6 compliant label to avoid double counting between companies and NDCs. However, VCUs used for voluntary carbon market purposes do not require Article 6 or other Paris-related program VCU labels, though labelled VCUs may be used for voluntary market transactions if desired. Finally, Plan Vivo requires evidence that the credits are not used by another program, which may require details on corresponding adjustments.

Thus, this review emphasizes the significant complexity associated with addressing double counting and related considerations of climate benefits within CF projects. As summarized in the Table 6 below, different standards analyse vary in their degree of risk consideration. While the risks of double issuance and double use are fairly well developed, the same cannot be said for double claims, especially those under the Paris Agreement. The establishment of a registry by standards enables achieving a level of transparency that mitigates primary-level risks. With the rapid evolution of voluntary mechanisms such as SBTi and the undefined provisions under Article 6, it appears challenging for the VCM standards to effectively prevent more subtle risks of double counting. This is a topic that will need clarification within the framework of the CRCF. For further

details on this subject, the MARVIC group has authored a more comprehensive note intended for DG Clima to convey the complexity of the issue.

Table 6 Assessment of double counts accounting in 11 SOC methodologies.

	Double issuance	Double use	Double counting	Double claiming
Plan vivo	Public Markit Registry grouping all Plan Vivo Certificates issued, transacted, and retired.	Third-party registry allocating unique serial numbers, ensuring that there is no double-counting or double-selling of PVCs.		-
Verra	Public Verra registry ensuring uniqueness of projects and credits. Transparent listing of registered projects and projects pursuing registration, issued and retired units, and enables the trading of units.	Once a unit is retired all rights and corresponding Environmental Benefits are extinguished for Verra and all parties involved.	If a project proponent is a buyer or seller of a product which emissions footprint is changed by the project activities, the project proponent shall make a statement on their website.	VCUs used for voluntary carbon market purposes do not require Article 6 or other Paris-related program VCU labels.
LBC	Available tracking file for projects and carbon units including quantity and type of verified emission reductions recognized, name of the RE owner and intermediary if applicable.	Carbon units are not transferable to a second buyer.	-	Considers there is no double claiming between the VCM and states inventory.
Gold Standard	Public GS Impact Registry tracking carbon credits and associated SDGs impacts.	Project developer must demonstrate full and uncontested legal ownership of any products, accepting the Impact Registry Terms of Use. Account Holders that fail to comply with requirements may face the suspension of their access to the Impact Registry, delisting, and other penalties under the Terms of Use.	Relies on the upcoming GHG protocol land sector and removal guidance. Requirements for Credits Authorized for Use Under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement. Impact Registry enables carbon credits to be labeled as authorized and correspondingly adjusted under Article 6.	-
UK woodland carbon code	Public UK land carbon registry. All projects, documentation, carbon units,	Each unit is allocated a unique serial number.	Once sold, each unit must be retired from the registry, the buyer must be clearly defined.	-

UK peatland code	assignments and retirements are accessible.		Considers there is no double claiming between the VCM and states inventory.	
MoorFutures	Public registry managed by respective sales point, serve as a platform for seller and buyer to collaborate.	-	-	-

-No information was provided in the methodology

3. Conclusion

3.1 Synthesis

In conclusion, this analysis highlighted a notable alignment in the qualitative criteria considered across different methodologies, however, the approaches to these criteria exhibit substantial diversity. This diversity goes beyond differences in terminology or categorization; it influences the entire process, from the selecting of parameters to the methodologies used for collecting, analysing and communicating the data. For instance, although additionality is universally acknowledged, its assessment and demonstration vary significantly (financial, regulatory, barriers analysis, common practices, or climatic benefits). Similarly, while most methodologies recognize the importance of permanence, their methods for estimating and ensuring it diverge (buffer amount, risks considered, assessment toll). Leakage is also inconsistently addressed, with some methodologies providing more robust mechanisms for leakage prevention than others. Moreover, the issue of double counting presents a complex challenge that is approached differently by each methodology. The risks associated with double counting varies from the simple fact of not crediting the same project twice to ensuring no double counting with state NDCs under the Paris agreement. Finally, the establishment of baselines varies widely among methodologies, although specific baseline is almost always preferred.

This wide-ranging variability in methodology approaches raises significant concerns about the quality and comparability of carbon credits traded within the voluntary carbon market. Without standardized approaches to address these key criteria, there is a risk that carbon credits may not accurately represent the true climate benefits of projects, potentially leading to market distortions and undermining the credibility of carbon markets as effective tools for climate change mitigation. Thus, there is a pressing need for greater harmonization and transparency in carbon farming methodologies to ensure consistency, reliability, and integrity in the evaluation and trading of carbon credits. By working towards common standards and best practices, stakeholders can enhance the credibility and effectiveness of carbon markets, thereby contributing to more robust and sustainable climate change mitigation efforts globally.

3.2 Compatibility with QU.AL.ITY criteria

Overall, there is a convergence between the European Commission's QU.A.L.ITY criteria and the standards that have already been developed. When it comes to additionality, the EU requires consideration of regulatory and financial additionality, as is the case of most standards. It also developed a new way of attesting additionality by considering that if the standardised baseline is used then financial and regulatory additionality is necessarily demonstrated. This reduces the administrative burden where the use of the standardised baseline is possible (Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products, 2024). Moreover, the last provisional agreement available goes further than any analysed methodology by imposing a biodiversity co-benefit criterion for carbon farming projects. Although not explicitly mentioned in terms of additionality, this can be viewed as a mandatory ecological criterion, similar to Gold Standard.

Regarding double counting, the EU proposes to establish a registry like all existing standards. Until its implementation, the CRCF will rely on the registries of these existing standards. It also introduces a clause indicating the use of CRCF credits in the NDCs of member states, revealing an issue between double counting among states and businesses.

In terms of permanence, the EU proposes something innovative by acknowledging the reversibility of carbon storage in nature-based projects and defining a category for temporary storage for carbon farming sequestration units. This is also the case for baselines where the Commission proposes a counterintuitive system based on standardized default baselines, and if not possible, the ability to establish specific baselines.

However, the consideration of leakages is not yet fully clarified and is scarcely addressed in the document. In conclusion, the content of the CRCF remains at the surface level, and it will be necessary to more precisely define these criteria in the methodologies that will follow the adoption of the regulation to have a workable and deployable framework.

For a more thorough exploration of challenges in additionality, double counting, permanence, leakage, and baseline issues, readers are encouraged to consult the MARVIC Deliverable 1.2 Draft Rules and Guiding Principles for the MRV Framework (Lanckriet et al., 2024). This document offers an evaluation of the limitations in existing methodologies, forward-thinking solutions, recommended practices for forthcoming strategies, and expert analyses.

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